

HISTORY OF LOCAL SELF GOVERNMENT IN ANDHRA

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The concept of Local Self Government was age old. It was not in the sense in which it is understood today. Even in the pre Vijayanagar days, the local assemblies called 'Ur' performed all functions on behalf of the people living in the villages. In the Agraharas Bramahadeya villages assemblies known as the Sabha played an important role such as collecting taxes, redressing public grievances and exercising judicial functions.

Local Bodies under composite Madras State: The pattern of Local Administration in the Madras presidency did not get any statutory basis till the enactment of the Towns Improvement Act X, 1865 and the Local Funds Act 1871. Edward Maltby, the collector of South Arcot District and engineer, under the supervision of Board of Revenue, a fund was raised for being spent on district roads in 1854. By 1863 this local fund collection raised up to 4 lakh rupees. Which consists revenue contributions; ferry tolls surplus proceeds of cattle pounds, and other miscellaneous items. This arrangement continued until the local Legislative Act (Act III) of 1866 passed and authorize the government to levy a road cess at 3.5 % on the annual rent of land. This statutory arrangement enabled the provincial government to rise this fund up to 26 lakhs. Thus, a semi voluntary funds became statutory¹.

The year 1870 has more significance in the history of local self-government in India. In that year Lord Mayo's historical resolution on decentralization was passed. Which emphasized the desirability of associating Indians in administration². Mayo directed the provincial authorities to enlist the active assistance of educated Indians in organizing and functioning of local government³. But with this resolution of 1870 the progress was not up to the expectation.

Despite that, a large income from local taxes had been secured entrusted to local bodied. The number of municipalities had increased. To look after the communication, education and sanitation District Boards had been created⁴. But local bodies were nominated by the British officials and the Indians remind deprived of participation in their functioning.

Rippon's Resolution of 1882: The magna carta of the local self-government in India is the Historic resolution of 1882 of Lord Rippon. The salient feature of the resolution is that the local self-government should be an instrument of political education. It explained clearly how to achieve this aim throughout British India. The resolution clearly emphasized the government control on local bodies should be minimized. The sole aim of the resolution is on political training. Lord Rippon took important initiative to strengthen local bodies such as, increasing the non-official representation, introduction of the system of election as widely as possible, as far as possible the chairman should be non-official, government control should be minimized and

local bodies were to be given full autonomy to impose and collect local taxes⁵. As per the resolution various enactments were made in different provinces during the 1883-84, to establish local self-government. By 1901, the system of election had been introduced and the proportion of nominated and elected members was fixed⁶. Post Rippon's period development in local bodies was slow during the Viceroyalty of Dufferin, Elgin and Curzon no improvement was made⁷.

Royal Commission on Decentralization 1909: In 1907 the British government appointed the Royal Commission to consider the devolution of powers between center and states. In ancient and medieval India village was basic unit of local self-government. But after the advent of British rule its importance had suffered. The commission pleaded for the revival of the village community. The committee recommend more powers to Sub District Boards or Taluk Boards and municipalities. For the committee recommended for minimizing the participation of government officers in the local body elections. The vice chairman of municipal council should be an elected non official⁸.

Resolution of 1915: The functioning of local bodies were slow. The government of India resolution 1950 mainly focused attention impediments in local self-government success. Lack of proper local revenues, lack of enthusiasm of the local people to participate in public life, no adequate sources of taxation, sectarian differences were identified as the main impediments⁹. Changes in the Functions of the Municipal Boards, Rural and Panchayat Boars were suggested. Majority of the members of the local bodies should elected, the collector of the district was relieved of his executive control over the municipalities. Municipalities were given full powers on taxation and preparing budgets¹⁰.

Resolution of 1917: The political scenario in India changed due to the first world war. The British government sought the support from people to the world safe for democracy. Indian leaders demanded the government to take substantial efforts to establish democratic rule in the country. In response to that Montague, the Secretary of State for India, made the famous declaration on 20th Aug 1917 regarding the future policy of the British towards India. The declaration emphasized about the introduction of responsible government in India¹¹. This declaration covered the domain of Local Self-government, rural boards and municipal council. It was expected in the declaration that the local self-government was the great training ground from which a sense of responsibility could be felt¹².

Resolution of 1918: The government of India evolved a more advanced policy of local self-government in 1918. Three fourth of the seats in municipalities were to be filled in by election process Minorities are to be nominated and not by the system of proportional representation¹³. The chairperson of the local bodies should be elected by the members and not nominated by

the government . Municipalities were given autonomy in preparing budget and in powers of taxation. The resolution approved the proposal for establishing a separate department of local self-government in the provinces¹⁴ . In fact, this resolution emphasized on making the local self-government as representative of the people the people as possible whom they served. The need to transfer real power to the local self-government without any outside interference was urged¹⁵. This resolution became more significance in the context of the proposed Diarchy.

Government of India Act, 1919: The government of India Act of 1919 inaugurated new changes in the field of local self-government. In this period so many amendment acts on local self-government was passed. The local bodies were freed from many restrictions in preparing its budget. Election process was further democratized. Earlier a civil servant was acting as the president to the all-Municipal bodies and a few Districts Local Boards. With this act this practice disappeared. Above all the executive power passed into the hands of elected members¹⁶ . Thus, the local self-government moved into the direction of democracy.

The independence movement coincided with the process of the democratization of local self-government. These reforms contributed the men of capability, caliber and dedication to enter the local bodies. Some of them were Sardar Patel, Jawaharlal Nehru, Purueshotham Das Tandan and from Madras Presidency C Rajagopala Chari, E V Ramaswamy Nayakar, Kamaraj etc., Local Self-government gave them training for their political career and their participation in the local administration¹⁷ .

In this period the India taxation enquiry committee of 1925 and Simon commission made some references to the local bodies. The committee referred the problems of taxation in central, provincial and local level as well Indian taxation enquiry committee come to the conclusion after a careful examination of the entire taxation problem, the finances of the local bodies are in sufficient to meet the services for their respective constituents¹⁸ .

Simon Commission 1927: To review the government of India Act 1919 British government appointed Simon Commission. The commission made in depth and thorough study regarding the problems faced by local bodies. The commission remarked that the efficiency of the local bodies to a great extent depended up on the control exercised by the provincial government over local bodies. Simon commission also observed the rigid state control over the finances of the local bodies. The local bodies were facing severe financial crunch to their basic requirements. When compare to the government of India act of 1919, the Simon commission's recommendations were retrogressive in the matters of local bodies autonomy¹⁹ . The municipal councils of Eluru, Vijayawada, Kurnool, Tirupati and Srikakulam

passed resolutions in favor of boycott . The government selected Guntur and Ongole as the two towns in Andhra for visit of Simon commission²⁰ .

The Government of India Act of 1935: The British government passed the government of India act of 1935 and introduced provincial autonomy. Local self-government in rural and urban areas were further strengthened. In this aspect the provincial governments passed several laws. The government of India act 1935 abolished the Diarchy in provinces and increased the powers of elected legislature. Popular governments in provinces which started functioning from 1937 introduced many notable reforms in local bodies. Now local self-government began to acquire a new stable base. Further, in this attempt were made to expand the network of village panchayats but unfortunately differences with the British government and the second world war, the congress governments in provinces resigned in 1939²¹ .

Local Self Government in Independent India: The independence of the country in 1947 attained much significance in the history of local self-government. after independence, there was self-government at all levels i.e local, provincial and central. For the first time it enabled the local self-government to function under an atmosphere of freedom. Independent government felt more concern about socio- economic development of rural areas.

In order to solve the socio economic problems of the country, with high hopes government launched Community Development Program (CDP) . The program claimed to be more advanced and comprehensive in nature. The government divided the country into five thousand community development blocks and along with the first five-year plan. The community development program introduced as country wide program. At the time of introduction of the program the Government of India made substantial economic help made for various development programs. To look after the programs, block development officer was appointed at block level. The new program assumed economic prosperity by community participation.

Constitutional position: The constituent assembly made a provision in the Directive principles of state policy, by including article 40, which reads, "The state shall take steps to organize village panchayats and endow them with such powers and authority as may be necessary to enable them to function as units of self-government " ²² . However, initially there was no suitable legislation was enacted at central level and state level to implement it.

The Congress Village Panchayat Committee 1954: To implement five years plan the question of grassroots level development became important. In this connection, the congress party appointed a high-power committee consisting of K N. Katju, Jagajivan Ram, K. D. Malaviya, Gulzarilat Nanda, Gurumush Nihal Singh and Sriram Narayana etc., to consider the feasibility of establishing local bodies in the rural areas. The committee in its report submitted on 19th July 1954 recommended the establishment of panchayat Raj. This was followed by setting up of the

official committee in 1956 on initiative of the national development council (NDC) by the government of India, under the chairmanship of Balwanthrai Mehta, to examine the whole problem of panchayat Raj and suggest way and means for its introduction.

Balwant Roy Mehta Committee: In the history of panchayat raj institutions, the appointment of Balwant Roy Mehta was a mile stone. The committee had to study the problems connected with the linking of rural bodies with democratic institutions at higher levels and organization of district administration so that the popular governments should take over the complete general administration. The committee noted that for many years decentralization of power and responsibility had not taken place below the provinces. The committee recommended a three-tier system for local self-government at grass root level. All powers should be transfer to the popularly elected body which will have the entire charges of all development²³.

Balwanth Rai Mehta committee submitted its report in November 1957 and National Development Council approved the report in January 1958. The NDC recognized the importance of giving responsibility for development to the elected representatives. The NDC clearly stated that how the recommendations should be applied in a matter to be decided by the state governments. The NDC stressed that there should be a three tier system of local bodies from the district to the village and there should be clear transfer of power and responsibility to local bodies²⁴.

On the basis of broad recommendations of the Balwant Roy Mehta committee the country covered with panchayat raj institutions in the preceding years. In various states there are four different patterns of local bodies in existence. The standard mode of three tier system, originally introduced in Andhra Pradesh and Rajasthan on 2 Oct 1959.

Andhra Pradesh government before implementing the Balwant Ray Mehta committee recommended three tier system, in July 1958. A P government made an experiment in 20 blocks in different districts. Later government enacted Andhra Pradesh Panchayat Samithi's and Zilla parishads Act of 1959. Later village panchayats were reorganized with Gram Panchayat Act of 1964². In three tier panchayat raj system 15789 village panchayats, 322 panchayat samithies, 21 Zillaparishads were formed.

M T Raju Committee: Panchayat Raj institutions have been changing continuously since beginning. In 1964 a high-level committee was constituted to reorganize the blocks. Administrative reforms commission examined the functioning of local bodies and recommended number of reforms. M T Raju committee constituted in 1967. The committee looked into the functioning of local bodies and recommended administrative reforms. The government accepted M.T. Raju committee recommendations and implemented them. District Development Boards come into existence. Agriculture and Industrial development planning was the main functions of the boards²⁶.

Jalagam Vengal Rao Committee 1968: The newly created District Development Boards invited political criticism. The political parties alleged that it increased the bureaucratic interference in the local body issues. Even they alleged that even it was against the recommendations of Balwant Ray Mehatha committee. Congress legislative party committee under the leadership of Jalagam Vengala Rao, made so many recommendations for panchayat raj bodies reorganization. The following are some of the important recommendations.

- a) The committee recommended to adjust the blocks equally with Revenue Taluk areas.
- b) The committee recommended to reduce the number of standing committees.
- c) The committee recommended to abolish District /development Boards and asked to handover its responsibilities to Zillaparishads.
- d) The committee recommended to bring all the district level officers under the purview of Zilla parishad
- e) The committee recommend to nominate SC, ST women candidates in standing committees

Narasimhan Committee 1972: In 1971 the government of Andhra Pradesh appointed a committee under the chairmanship of C Narasimhan a retired IAS officer to examine and recommend necessary proposals for its reorganization. The committee made the following recommendations.

- 1) The committee recommend for direct elections of panchayat sarpanch.
- 2) Members of panchayat Samithies should not be elected directly by people not by sarpanches. The Samithi members would elect president and vice president of panchayat Samithi's.
- 3) Zillaparishad members also should be elected by people. All presidents of panchayat Samithi's would be an ex – officio members of Zillaparishad.
- 4) The committee felt that MLA s and MPs need not be members of panchayat Samithi's and Zillaparishads
- 5) The district collectors need not be an ex – officio member of Zillaparishad.
- 6) Contesting candidates to rural local bodies should be used party symbols . But political parties can field their members in local body elections²⁷ .
- 7) The committee emphasized for preparation of plans; district should be taken as unit. District funds should be in the purview of Zillaparishad. The committee also asked to allocate separate funds for welfare schemes.

Ashok Mehatha Committee 1977: The Janatha party government appointed a High level committee under the chairmanship of Ashok Mehatha on 12 Dec 1977 After two years I e 1978 the committee submitted its report. The committee observed panchayat raj institutions are mostly dominated by privileged sections

of the society. The committee recommended for a two-tier system of panchayat raj institutions with Mandal panchayat at ground level and Zillaparishad at top. Ashok Mehatha committee emphasized the importance of gram Sabha. Committee desired the Chief election Commissioner of the state should conduct elections to panchayat raj institutions on the party basis. Only some states like Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Bengal etc., accepted some of its recommendations and made attempts to implement them.

For the sake of administrative decentralization, the government of Andhra Pradesh established 1104 revenue mandals on the 25th May 1985 in the place of 305 Taluks and 1084 revenue firkas. The sole aim of the Andhra government To establishment of revenue mandal system was to bring the administration Nearer to the common man. On that basis each revenue mandal consists of a Population of 35000 to 55000 depending on population density. On 26 July 1986 The government passed the bill to create Mandal Prajaparishids, Zilla Praja Parishads and Zilla Pranalika Abjivrudhi Mandals.

G V K Rao Committee 1985: To examine panchayat raj institutions government appointed G V K Rao committee. The committee strongly emphasized the role of local bodies in rural development. It recommended adequate government support to strengthen local bodies. The committee recommended to hand over the planning and execution of rural development programs to the panchayat raj institutions. The committee emphasized the importance of panchayat samithies in rural development.

L M Singvi Committee 1986: The committee carefully studied the functioning of Local bodies. It considered the gram Sabha as the base of decentralized democracy. The committee emphasized that panchayat raj institutions should be constitutionally recognized, preserved and protected. Further it recommended noninvolvement of political parties in the panchayat raj institutions elections. But Sarkaria commission opposed the idea of giving constitutional status to Panchayat raj institutions. However, the idea of constitutional status to the local bodies gained momentum in the late 1980s.

73rd Constitutional Amendment Act 1992: To strengthen the panchayat raj institutions in the country, the 73rd constitutional amendment bill introduced in parliament in Sep 1992. The central government notified it in the official Gazette on 20th April 1993. It is a major initiative to bring revolutionary changes in the structure and functioning of panchayat raj system of the country. In the history of democratic decentralization the 73rd constitution amendment act 1992 is indeed a major mile stone.

References:

1. B D Misra, "The Administrative History of India 1834 – 1947 ". Oxford university press, London 1970, P .166.
2. J M Thakur, Development of Local Self Government in Bombay and Sawrastra, Bombay 1957, P 3
3. T M Nair, Principles and Practices of Municipal Government, Madras P. 30
4. Manual of the Administration of the Madras Presidency, Vol. I P. 250.
5. L P Mathur, Lord Ripon's Administration in India 1800 84 AD., O P . cit., P . 184.
6. R . Argal, Muncipal Government in India OP cit., P 23
7. Hugh Tinker, The Foundations of Local Self Government in India – Pakistan and Burma, OP., cit P. 67.
8. K K Pillai, History of Local Self Government in the Madras Presidency 1850 -1919, OP, cit., P 67.
9. The Gazette of India, dated 1st May 1925 PP 1175 – 91.
10. M Venkatarangaiah and M. Pattabhiram (Ed.) , Local Self Government in India , OP . cit., P. 185
11. A B Keith: OP., cit., Vol – I P 394
12. Govt of India Resolution on NO. 41 dated 16th May 1918.
13. R Chandra G . Shah, The Growth of Local Self – Government in the Provence of Bombay since 1858, OP, cit P 28.
14. K K Pillai, History of Local Government in Madras Presidency 1850 – 1919 op, cit P. 42.
15. The Gazette of India, dated 25th May 1918 P 981 – 93.
16. S R Maheshwari, OP, Cit ., PP. 20 – 21 .
17. Ibid
18. Reports of Local Finance Enquiry committee OP , Cit ., PP 33 – 34 .,Arthur Berriedale Keith , A Constitutional History of India 1600 - 1935 (London 1969) PP . 287 – 293.
19. Arthur Berriedale Keith, A Constitutional History of India 1600 – 1935. (London 1935) PP 287 – 293
20. Prof. P Raghunath Rao, History and Culture of Andhra Pradesh, Sterling Publishers Pvt., Noida 2020 P – 201.
21. Ramesh Dutt, The Economic History of India under early British rule Motilal Baharisdas, Delhi 1937 – pp – 151 152.
22. S V Samanth, Village Panchayat woth special reference to Bombay state local self-government institute, Bombay, 1957 p. 25.
23. S V Samanth, Village Panchayat woth special reference to Bombay state local self-government institute, Bombay, 1957 p. 27

24. Balwant Roy Mehatha Committee Report section – 2 planning commission, New Delhi
1958 P 23.
25. Andhra Pradesh Darsani Visalandra publications P. 656.
26. Prof. K Venkatachalam, D. Suram Naidu, Andhra Pradesh Darsini, Visalandra publication
P. 659,